

A close-up photograph of a brown spider on a surface of reddish-brown soil and small, irregular rocks. The spider is positioned on the left side of the frame, facing right. Its body is a light brown color, and its legs are thin and translucent. The background is a textured surface of soil and rocks, with some small green plants visible in the upper left.

THE
ORSOLOBIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The Orsolobidae is represented by 30 genera and 188 species. From South Africa three genera represented by four species are known. Two of the species are Western Cape endemics *Afrilobus australis* Griswold & Platnick, 1987 and *Calculus bicolor* Purcell, 1910 with *Afrilobus capensis* Griswold & Platnick, 1987 known from the Western and Northern Cape. Only *Azania lobus lawrencei* Griswold & Platnick, 1987 has a wide distribution recorded from four provinces. None of the species are of special concern.

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FAMILY ORSOLOBIDAE Cooke, 1965

The Orsolobidae is represented by 30 genera and 188 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). The first orsolobids were described from Africa. From South Africa three genera represented by four endemic species are known.

COMMON NAME: Six-eyed ground spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: small spiders (2-5 mm). Colour: pale yellow to white with purplish pigmentation; abdomen dorsally suffused with purplish pigment interrupted by pale hairline chevrons in *Afrilobus*; markings uniform or absent in *Azania lobus*.

Carapace broadly oval, narrowed anteriorly; six eyes; posterior lateral eyes behind anterior lateral eyes, widely spaced (4:2). Abdomen oval sometimes with chevron markings (*Afrilobus*); spinnerets slender, subequal in length; anterior spinnerets three-segmented; colulus small in *Afrilobus*, large and setose in *Azania lobus*. Legs long and slender, uniformly clothed in ciliate setae; no scopulae; presence of an elevated tarsal organ distinct for orsolobids; two biserially dentate paired claws, onychium and spatulate claw tufts.

LIFESTYLE: Orsolobids are ground dwellers, wandering around in low vegetation, humus, leaf litter and moss frequently in Afromontane forests. However, one species *Afrilobus capensis* has been collected from fynbos.

TAXONOMIC NOTE: The genera of Africa described by Griswold & Platnick (1987).

Orsolobidae. a: *Afrilobus* sp., female, dorsal view; b: line-drawing showing leg lengths; c: tarsus, showing claws with spatulate setae; d: tarsus of leg, showing enlarged tarsal organ; e: carapace, lateral view, showing raised areas on sternum; f: male palp, lateral view (After Griswold & Platnick, 1987; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997).

GENUS *AFRILOBUS* Griswold & Platnick, 1987

Genus represented by three African species of which two are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Afrilobus Six-eyed ground spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Afrilobus capensis* Griswold & Platnick, 1987

MORPHOLOGY: Small size 3.4-3.5 mm. Orsolobids with abdominal dorsum suffused with purple pigment interrupted only by narrow, pale chevrons. Carapace broadly oval; six eyes with anterior row with four (4:2); chelicerae with two promarginal and two retromarginal teeth with retromarginals more widely spaced than promarginals. Sternum not produced at labial border, with long, triangular extensions to, and slight elevations opposite, each coxa. Abdomen oval; abdominal dorsum suffused with purple pigment interrupted only by narrow, pale chevrons; colulus small, pigmented lobe. Legs slender with two tarsal claws, onychium and spatulate claw tufts' with spines present on tibiae and metatarsi III and IV, and occasionally on tibiae I and II; claws with outer row of teeth not restricted to lateral flange, with tufts of few spatulate hairs; palpal claw of female smooth; tarsal organ relatively low, with 3 to 18 short marginal cuticular lobes and 2 to 3 short receptor lobes

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers

TAXONOMY: The genus was described by Griswold & Platnick (1987).

Afrilobus sp. after Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2006)

Eye pattern and tarsal claws Photo ASD

Afrilobus australis Griswold & Platnick, 1987

COMMON NAME: Knysna Six-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Griswold & Platnick (1987) from the Knysna Forest. (EEO=746km²; AOO=12 km²; 42-353 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Knysna Forest (-34.03, 23.03); Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44).

LIFESTYLE: Orsolobids are ground dwellers, wandering around in low vegetation, humus, leaf litter and moss. Sampled from the Fynbos and Forest biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006) and Diepwalle Forest Station.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Described by Griswold & Platnick (1987). Known only from the female.

Afrilobus australis from De Hoop Nature Reserve Photo Charles Haddad

Afrilobus capensis Griswold & Platnick, 1987

COMMON NAME: Cape Six-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Griswold & Platnick (1987) from the Cederberg Wilderness Area. The species is known from two provinces (EOO=2 639 km²; AOO=24 km²; 176-1493 m a.s.l.). There are no known threats to the species and it is protected in the Namaqua National Park and Cederberg Wilderness Area. As there is a lot of natural habitat remaining between the two known locations, and this species is likely to be under collected, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION ON SOUTH AFRICA: **Western Cape:** Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.16, 18.89). Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal. CIB17.1, 522 m a.s.l. (-32.2873, 19.235); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.2644, 19.1226); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, CIB13.1, 1557 m a.s.l.(-32.3478, 19.1709); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, CIB13.2, 1531 m a.s.l. (-32.3472, 19.1719); Cederberg Wilderness Area 9.3, 1551 m a.s.l. (-32.4, 19.09); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Crystal pools CIB14.3, 1289 m a.s.l. (-32.3448, 19.1383). **Northern Cape:** Namaqua National Park Soebatsfontein (-30.11, 17.59).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running soil dweller found mostly in humus, under bushes or large stones. Sampled with pitfall traps from the Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species and it is protected in the Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Described by Griswold & Platnick (1987). Known only from the male.

After Griswold & Platnick (1987)

Tarsal organ from leg IV and tarsal claws after Griswold & Platnick (1987)

***Azania*lobus Griswold & Platnick, 1987**

Genus represented by a single species recorded known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Azania*lobus* Six-eyed ground spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Azania*lobus *lawrencei* Griswold & Platnick, 1987

MORPHOLOGY: Relatively large orsolobids (total length 3.4-4.5); pale with abdominal markings uniform to absent. Body and legs finely setose. Cephalothorax, abdomen, and legs pale yellowish white (in alcohol); black pigment surrounding eyes and extending between the anterior lateral and posterior median eyes. Carapace broadly oval; six eyes with anterior row with four (4:2). Abdomen cylindrical, without scuta; abdominal markings uniform to absent. Legs slender with two tarsal claws, onychium and spatulate claw tufts' with spines present on tibiae and metatarsi III and IV, and occasionally on tibiae I and II; claws with outer row of teeth not restricted to lateral flange, with tufts of few spatulate hairs; palpal claw of female smooth; tarsal organ relatively low, with 3 to 18 short marginal cuticular lobes and 2 to 3 short receptor lobes.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers

TAXONOMY: The genus was described by Griswold & Platnick (1987).

*Azania*lobus sp. female from Kalkrivier Dam NR Photo Nicolette Josling

*Azania*lobus *lawrencei* female from Wyndford Guest Farm Photo Peter

Azania lobus lawrencei Griswold & Platnick, 1987

COMMON NAME: Lawrence's Six-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Griswold & Platnick (1987) from Mariepskop, in Mpumalanga. It has also been recorded Lesotho. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=161 885 km²; AOO=48 km²; 834-2329 m a.s.l.) and protected in five protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range it is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.27, 29.2); Fouriesburg, Wyndford Guest Farm (-28.7, 28.24). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Drakensberg (-24.62, 30.88). **Limpopo:** New Agatha Forest (-24.03, 30.08); Mara.-23.04, 29.66); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Springbokvlakte, Bekendevelei (-25.01, 28.88); Vhembe Biosphere Entabeni State Forest (-23.0129,30.2498). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Carolina (-26.1545,30.1515).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running soil dweller. Sampled from the Grassland, Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Platberg Nature Reserve, Ngome State Forest and Entabeni State Forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Described by Griswold & Platnick (1987) and known from both sexes. Cephalothorax, abdomen, and legs pale yellowish white; black pigment surrounding eyes and extending between eyes; abdomen with faint mottling on dorsum, diffuse purple-brown ring surrounding base of spinnerets.

After Griswold & Platnick (1987)

Azania lobus lawrencei female from Wyndford guesdt Farm Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *CALCULUS* Purcell, 1910

Genus represented by a single species recorded known from South Africa. *Calculus* Purcell, 1910 was transferred from Oonopidae to the Orsolobidae (Platnick et al. 2012).

COMMON NAME: Calculus Six-eyed ground spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Calculus bicolor* Purcell, 1910:

MORPHOLOGY: Body size 4 mm. Colour pale yellow; abdomen with broad infuscate patch; narrowly blackened on each side of spinnerets. Carapace broadly ovate; ocular area transverse; anterior eye row almost straight; median eyes large; anterior lateral eyes smallest of six, Abdomen, and legs pale yellowish white;

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers. Several specimens were sample from Cape Flats near Princess and Zeekoei Vleis.

TAXONOMY: The genus was described by Purcell (1910)

Calculus sp. from Sani Pass possibly new sp.? Photo ASD

***Calculus bicolor* Purcell, 1910**

COMMON NAME: Calculus Six-eyed ground spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1910) from Flats near Princess and Zeekoei Vleis. Known only from the type locality (EOO=>100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 834-2329 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Cape Flats Princess and Zeekoei Vlei (-34.02,18.6).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running soil dweller.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Development on the Cape Flats could be a threat for the species. Some more sampling is needed to determine if the species are still there and the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Described by Purcell (1910) and known from both sexes but without illustrations.

UNDETERMINED

Species from Dullstroom

Species from Sani Pass

From Free State N. Josling

From Bloemfontein R. Steenkamp

Wyndford guest Farm

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